

THERMALLY CONDUCTIVE CELLULOSE-BASED SUBSTRATES FOR FLEXIBLE ELECTRONICS

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Abstract: *The use of renewable biopolymers in advanced (opto)electronics and wearable sensor devices has attained extensive attention recently, above all, to replace non-biodegradable dielectric thermoplastic polymers (e.g. polyimide/PI, polyethylene/PE, and polyvinylidene fluoride/PVDF) while maintaining the device's flexibility and increasing their recyclability. Nanocellulose/NC has gained particular attention due to its inherent biocompatibility, cost-effectiveness, and film-forming properties. However, all of these substrates are thermal insulators, while attached electronic components produce heat by Joule (resistive) effect during operation, thus affecting their function adversely, while also softening the thermoplastics. The thermal diffusivity of NC films can be obtained by reducing the thermal resistance at the interface between the cellulose fibrils/crystals with an increased interaction through their highly aligned anisotropic structure and/or introduced thermally-conductive 2D nanofillers. In this work, the films have been prepared from semi-crystalline cellulose nanofibrils (CNF) and the addition of 2D hexagonal boron nitrides (hBNs) of different lateral sizes (100 nm to 150 μ m) by pressure-filtration to examine their impact on the films' morphological and thermal dissipation (through-plane, in-plane) properties. In the next stage, the up-scalable slot-die coating technology was used to study the coatability of the most promising formulations onto the paper substrate. A uniform and relatively high coat weight (19 g/m²) was achieved by using CNC-hBN suspensions, leading to good coverage of the paper's surface and an improved thermal conductivity in both substrate directions, through- and in-plane.*

Keywords: nanocellulose, 2D hBN, films, slot-die coating, heat dissipation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thin, light and flexible dielectric substrates are typically still made from fossil/fuel-based thermoplastic polymers (Zhao et al. 2023) due their advantage of a smooth surface suitable for (opto)electronics device fabrication, high thermal stability (>500 °C), mechanical toughness, chemical resistance, as well as excellent electrical insulation properties (dielectric constant of 3-4) and inherently low coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE 3-6 x 10⁻⁵ 1/K). However, they are thermal insulators, while on such a substrate attached electronic components like integrated circuits produce heat by Joule (resistive) effect during operation (Uyor et al. 2023) that becomes even more serious by being more miniaturized and complicated. If the heat dissipated is not discarded (or converted into the other one), it accumulates and affects the performance and reliability of electronic devices, while also softening the polymeric dielectric substrate. Flexible substrates with high enough thermal conductivity are thus urgently needed to improve thermal management and reach new applications, including active/intelligent packaging, healthcare (medical instruments, wearable devices), intelligent (robots,

industrial machinery), and automotive industries (electronics), smart cities (consumer electronics), and space/military systems (Baruh et al. 2023).

The nanocomposite films have attracted much attention recently by adding a small amount of highly thermally-conductive 2D layered nanofillers (like hexagonal boron nitrides / h-BN with ~ 600 W/mK in-plane and ~ 30 W/mK through-plane TC of a monolayer, density of ~ 2.2 g/cm³, elastic constant of 220–510 N/m and Young's modulus of 1 TPa) (Falın et al. 2017) through the specific structure construction (Uyor et al. 2023), thus combining the advantages of heat dissipation, light weight, high flexibility, and good processing performance (Wu et al. 2017). The added hBNs can also improve mechanical strength, electrical insulation (dielectric constant of ~ 6.9 at 1 MHz), and flame retardancy (temperature resistance above 700 °C) (Wu et al. 2022), allowing them to be applied in harsh environments.

By introduction of hBNs (loading up to 50 wt%) to CNF-based films, the in-plane TC of CNF can thus be increased from about 0.6 - 2 W/mK (Uetani K & Hatori 2017) up to ~ 12 W/mK (Xu et al. 2022), at loading below 50 wt%. Since phonon transport (and thus TC) is affected by the functional groups on the surfaces of the CNF, the lateral dimension of hBN sheets as well as their interactions and distribution into the CNF matrix, which all influence on inter-sheets thermal resistance, the TC of CNF/hBNs can be increased further by improving the bulk structuring and using differently large hBNs.

In this work, TC properties of TEMPO-oxidized CNF (CNF) films prepared by an up-scalable pressure filtration method were studied over a broad temperature (30 – 120 °C) range. Various weight percentages of few-layered hBNs of different (100 nm - 150 μ m) lateral sizes were included, to verify the impact of CNF on their self-assembly and interphase arrangement in such a composite films, and, consequently, through-plane and in-plane heat dissipation capacity. In the next stage, the up-scalable slot-die coating technology was used to study the coatibility of the most promising formulations onto the paper substrate and its TC properties.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

TEMPO-oxidized CNFs with chain-like structures, diameter of the 10-30 nm and length of a few (1–3) μ m, were prepared from bleached softwood pulp at the Stockholm University, Department of Chemistry (Sweden). The few-layered 2D hexagonal boron nitride (hBN) powders of low density (~ 2.2 g/cm³), high surface area (3-4 m²/g) and purity (>99%), and different lateral sizes were purchased from Nanografi (Ankara, Turkey) and Henze BNP AG (Lauben, Germany, respectively, and used as received. The isopropyl alcohol (IPA) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich GmbH (Germany). The pigment pre-treated paper (grammage of 51 ± 2 g/m², thickness of 78 ± 3 μ m) was obtained from Papirnica Vevče d.o.o. (Slovenia).

2.2 Preparation of pristine and composite films

For the preparation of the films, the initial 1.1 wt% CNF suspended in milli-Q water was diluted to 0.4 wt% by using a homogenizer Ultra-Turrax T18 (IKA-Werke GmbH & Co.KG, Germany). At the same time, various quantities of hBN were overnight pre-hydrated in few mL of IPA by magnetic stirring. Finally, different volumes of IPA-wetted hBNs were mixed with different volumes of the water-suspended TCNF by ultrasonic processor (VCX 750, Sonics & Materials, Inc., USA) for few min at 20% amplitude to get homogeneous CNF-hBN dispersions with a final 0.4-0.2 wt% of CNF and 0.1-1.2 wt% of hBN, containing 10 vol% or 50 vol% of IPA. The as prepared CNF/hBN dispersions were pressure filtered through a PVDF filter with a pore size of 0.22 μ m at 5 bars pressure by the dead-end mode using the HP4750 stirred cell (Sterlitech Co., USA) and 2.24 cm² of effective surface area to get wetted densely packed gel films (Fig. 1) with homogeneously distributed and parallelly aligned structure. The films were then left to dry at room temperature, removed from the filter paper, conditioned at 23 °C and 60% RH

for 24 h before being cold pressed for 24 h and 100 bars by a Perkin Elmer laboratory hydraulic press (Scientific Instruments, USA). The composite films were designated according to the weight percentage of CNF and hBN used, recalculated related to the total volume (generally 50 mL).

2.3 Slot-die coating of CNf-hBN suspension

A Challenger 175, semi-pilot & fully automated Sheet-to-Sheet (S2S) coating unit (Norbert Schläfli nsm AG, Switzerland) with an inline integrated 190 mm wide slot-die (TSE Troller AG, Switzerland) and NIR drying unit with 180 Ws/cm² of energy density (NIR252-125 Adphos GmbH, Germany) was used to control the coating speed (10 m/min), wet thickness deposition (40 μm), the drying speed (1 m/min) and power/time (40%, 120-180 sec); as shown on Fig. 2. A slot-die shim of 165 μm thickness was used, while the distance between the substrate and the slot lips was set to 100 μm.

2.4 Characterization

The thickness of the substrates was measured using a dial thickness gauge, F1000/30 (Käfer Messuhrenfabrik GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). The volumetric density (g/cm³) was calculated from the weight mass, diameter and thickness of the samples. The presented results are the arithmetic mean values and the Standard Deviations of at least two independent measurements, obtained after cold pressing. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging of sample surfaces and cross-sections were performed by using a low-vacuum scanning electron microscope, FEI Quanta 200 3D (Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc, USA). The thermal diffusivity in both through-plane and in-plane configuration was measured by the laser flash method using an LFA 467 HyperFlash (Netzsch Holding, Germany) at different temperatures (30 °C, 60 °C, 90 °C and 120 °C). At least three laser pulses (xenon of 10 J/pulse) for 20 μs were performed at each temperature. The samples were spray coated with graphene before the analysis. The thermal conductivity (TK, W/mK) was calculated as $TK = \alpha \times \rho \times C_p$, where α and ρ are the thermal diffusivity (TD, mm²/s) and density (g/cm³) of the substrate for each temperature, and C_p is the specific heat capacity (J/gK) measured with the classic sapphire method according to the standard procedure (User Com 7, Mettler Toledo GmbH, Schwerzenbach, Switzerland, 1998) using a differential scanning calorimeter Mettler Toledo DSC1 (Switzerland). For both TK and C_p determination samples were pre-heated to 140 °C, left for 15 min so that the adsorbed moisture was evaporated, then cooled to 5 °C, and thermostated at this temperature for 15 min before the dynamic measurement was performed at a rate of 10 K/min up to 120 °C; thus to determine the C_p of dried samples. Up to three measurements were made per each sample, and the results were given as an average value with a Standard Deviation.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of the hBN size and content on the morphology and thermal conductive (TC) properties of the CNF/hBN composite films are shown in Fig. 1. As shown in the SEM images, the micro-large hBNs has a typical plate-like morphology, consisting of a few nm thick nanosheets, stacked together in a multi-layered structure. The smoother surface, but randomly interwoven arranged cellulose fibrils, are visible in the cross-section of film containing the smallest (100 nm) and slightly aggregated hBNs, resulting in a relative high density (~2.2 g/cm³) without any impact on the improvement of TC compared to the reference film (prepared without hBN). By the addition of a larger and more homogenously distributed hBNs the fibrils and hBN platelets become more longitudinally oriented, but the film less densely structured (to ~2.0 g/cm³ for 20 μm hBN, to ~1.8 g/cm³ for 45 μm hBN and to ~1.6 g/cm³ for even larger 150 μm hBN) while given significant increase in both through-plane (for ~350%, to ~3.2 W/mK) and in-plane (for ~120%, to ~13.3 W/mK) TC (analysed by isotropic model) for film containing 150 μm hBN at the same weight ratio. By threefold addition of medium sized hBN (20 μm), the TC of such a composite film also increased from ~10.12 to ~13.8 W/mK, but with a significant deterioration of its bending properties (the film become more brittle). The slot-die coated CNf-hBN suspensions with the same weight ratio (1:1) resulted to ~19 g/m² of coating weight, but paper

thickness increased from ~ 8.5 to $\sim 14 \mu\text{m}$ (and density from ~ 0.75 to $\sim 0.92 \text{ g/cm}^3$) by using larger hBNs ($150 \mu\text{m}$), and, as expected, given more surface deposited and in-plane oriented platelets (Fig. 2). Although the coating weight and its density was relatively much lower than those used in the films, the in-plane TC of the paper improved by 77% (isotropically, to $\sim 8.4 \text{ W/mK}$) with the addition of better distributed $45 \mu\text{m}$ large particles at 30°C ; this effect increased linearly with increasing temperature which is attributed to the longer mean free path of phonon transport in such a hybrid structure.

Cellulose aggregates contain a lot of interfaces; the lower interfacial thermal resistance between semi-crystalline cellulose fibrils is thus derived from the strong surface interactions, such as hydrogen bonding and van der Waals forces. Such a molecular arrangement constrains the phonon transfer within the fibrils, thus resulting to lower TC as compared to composite structures containing hBNs. However, hydrophobic interactions between CNFs and hBNs also affect phonon transport not only in the axial direction (through-plane), but also in the radial direction (in-plane). The phonon mean free path, which is larger than the lateral size of hBN (and cellulose crystals), is also limited by boundary scattering of phonons on crystal grains; as a result, higher values of TC evaluated by the isotropic model than the anisotropic is evident, and the effect further increases with increasing the temperature. The presence of disorder and high density, which are more pronounced when using laterally smaller hBNs (both in films and paper-based coatings), further weaken phonon transport and the overall temperature dependence in such structures.

Figure 1: Morphology and thermal conductivity of CNF-hBN composite films.

Figure 2: Schematic presentation of the slot-die coating deposition with the morphology and in-plane thermal conductivity of the CNF-hBN coated paper.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The TC properties of CNF-hBN composite films as well as coated paper are highly affected by the arrangement of both the cellulose fibrils and hBNs within the matrix, their interactions and alignment. By using laterally larger hBNs, the anisotropic in-plane TC properties of such substrates are thus the highest among all tested formulations in both models used in their evaluation. This is particularly important as it allows for further improvement of the TC performance of such substrates with predefined heat dissipation properties required for specific applications, as printed electronics to ensure its optimal performance and reliability. On the other hand, substrates with randomly oriented composition exhibit higher isotropic TC (up to 14 W/mK at 30°C) similar to those obtained by other studies.

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5 REFERENCES

- Baruah R.K., Yoo H., Lee E.K. (2023) Interconnection technologies for flexible electronics: materials, fabrications, and applications. *Micromachines*, 14(6), pp. 1131.
- Falin A., Cai Q., Santos E.J.G., Scullion D., Qian D., Zhang R., Yang Z., Huang S., et.al. (2017). Mechanical properties of atomically thin boron nitride and the role of interlayer interactions. *Nat Commun.*, 22(8), pp. 15815.
- Uetani K., Hatori K. (2017) Thermal conductivity analysis and applications of nanocellulose materials. *Sci. Technol. Adv. Mater.*, 18, pp. 877.

Uyor U.O., Popoola A.P.I., Popoola O.M. (2023) Flexible dielectric polymer nanocomposites with improved thermal energy management for energy-power applications. *Front. Energy Res.*, 11, pp. 1114512.

Zhao C., Li Y., Liu Y., Xie H., Yu W. (2023) A critical review of the preparation strategies of thermally conductive and electrically insulating polymeric materials and their applications in heat dissipation of electronic devices. *Adv. Compos. Hybrid. Mater.*, 6(1), pp. 27.

Xu Y., Chen X., Zhang C. et al. (2022) Enhancing thermal conductivity and toughness of cellulose nanofibril/boron nitride nanosheet composites. *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 296, pp 119938.

Wu Y.P., Xue Y., Qin S., et al. (2017) BN nanosheet/polymer films with highly anisotropic thermal conductivity for thermal management applications. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, 9/49, pp. 43163.

Wu M., Zhou Y., Zhang H., Liao W. (2022) 2D boron nitride nanosheets for smart thermal management and advanced dielectrics. *Adv. Mater. Interfaces*, 9/25, pp. 2200610.